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People's Participation in Ensuring Good Governance at Local Levels in Bangladesh: A Study on Union Parishads

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Abstract

People's participation is a critical component of good governance, as it strengthens effective decision-making and improves the efficiency of local government practice. However, due to a variety of issues, people's participation in terms of ensuring good governance has been hampered, posing significant challenges to the effective service delivery of local government. In this regard, the study's primary goal was to explore the issue of people's participation in terms of ensuring good governance in Bangladesh. The study was carried out using a quantitative approach, with data gathered from primary sources. The findings of the study reveal that most of the rural people had no idea about the UP-standing committee (95%), open budget meeting (78%), and Union Parishad Act (83%). Similarly, it was found that 98% of rural people did not participate in the pre-open budget session and final open budget session, whereas 95% and 97% of rural people did not participate in the Ward Shaba and UP standing committees, respectively. Conversely, it was found that only 45% of rural people participated in UP village court activities. These findings demonstrate conclusively that individuals were less concerned in their engagement in various local government avenues to ensure good governance. In this vein, the research recommends that public education, awareness, and government-relevant policies might be successful in arousing citizens' concern about ensuring good governance at local government bodies, especially in UPs in Bangladesh.

Key Words: Good Governance, People's Participation, Local Government, Challenges, Practice, Bangladesh.

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1. Introduction

Bangladesh, as a developing country, has already achieved the distinction of having the fastest-growing economy due to its commitment to democracy and good governance at all levels. It is well understood that a country's long-term development is largely dependent on its governing system (Glass & Newig, 2019). Bangladesh has significantly improved human development indicators as well as good governance dimensions since the 1990s (Jahan, 2021). Bangladesh's constitution expressly states that the state shall make every effort to ensure equal opportunity for all citizens and shall take effective measures to eliminate social and economic inequality in order to ensure an equitable distribution of wealth and opportunities among citizens (Ahasan, 2018). The primary goal of this statement is to achieve a consistent level of sustainable development across the Republic (Aminuzzaman, 2006). In this regard, the most pressing issue is good governance, which refers to an ideal governing system that represents a paradigm shift in the role of governments. In particular, good governance is the active and fruitful interaction between the state and its people, and the key to its success resides with the forces that participate in political administration (Keping, 2018). However, good governance is critical for successful economic development (MIRA & HAMMADACHE, 2017). Accountability, transparency, efficiency and effectiveness, participation, the rule of law, and fairness are some of the traits of good governance. These traits make sure that society's priorities are widely accepted and that the voices of the most vulnerable and poorest people are heard when decisions are made about how to distribute resources for development (Hassan & Zeb, 2021). Besides, participation is one of the most essential indicators of good governance since it validates the involvement of the people in government decision-making (Uzzaman, 2010). Participation often refers to people's engagement in the decision-making process for implementing their fair share of the benefits of development programs as well as their involvement in attempts to assess such programs (Fitzgerald et al., 2016). Through the participation of the rural people, local government plays a crucial role in the exercise of democracy (Ahmed & Akter, 2021) and good governance in Bangladesh (Anam, 2019). However, the main obstacles in achieving good governance in Bangladesh include people's inadequate knowledge, poor education, and lack of interest as well as the authorities' weak accountability, poor transparency, the inappropriate practice of rule of law, poor inclusion, etc. Participating in the decision-making process and incorporating stakeholders may help to strengthen accountability, transparency, administrative efficiency, improve citizen awareness, etc. regarding ensuring good governance in Bangladesh. In this vein, how citizen participation may improve good governance in Bangladesh is a troubling matter. Therefore, the principal aim of this study was to explore how people's participation leads to ensuring successful good governance through people's participation at the Union Parishad level in Bangladesh.

However, the study significantly focused on the diverse challenges of people's participation in different avenues of local government that hinder practicing good governance at local government institutions, mostly UPs in Bangladesh. In addition, the study demonstrated the people's perception of their participation following a quantitative

approach that helped conclusively illustrate the existing status of people's participation as well as the practice of good governance at local government bodies (UPs) in Bangladesh.

2. Objectives of the Study

The principal objective of this study is to explore the state of people's participation in local government institutions (Union Parishad) in terms of ensuring good governance in Bangladesh.

The specific objectives are

- a) To identify the different avenues of people's participation in Union Parishads (UPs) regarding ensuring good governance in Bangladesh.
- b) To assess the people's perception of participation in the different avenues of Ups.
- c) To explore the major challenges of people's participation in the Union Parishads (UPs) in terms of practicing good governance in Bangladesh.

3. Review of Related Literature

Since the second half of the 1980s, the issues of governance and good governance have been evolving at the vanguard of the global agenda for progress. In recent times, the quality of governance is being measured as the key prerequisite for solving many problems and for socio-economic development in lower middle income countries like Bangladesh (Hasan et al., 2018). People's participation is thus one of the most essential prerequisites for achieving good governance (MIRA & HAMMADACHE, 2017).

4.1 Different Avenues of People's Participation in Union Parishads

Ahmed et al. (2022) examine a study on the most current trends in people's participation in the rural local government in Bangladesh. The study reveals that, despite the fact that public engagement in different forms of local government is fraught with difficulties, it is essential for bolstering decentralization in Bangladesh. The study's results indicate that political complexities, institutional corruption, low levels of education, and general ignorance make it very difficult for the majority of rural residents to participate in the different avenues of the Union Parishad in Bangladesh. As a result, the research suggests that increasing public awareness and ensuring the accountability and openness of service providers may boost people's participation in rural local government in Bangladesh (Ahmed et al., 2022).

As well, Uddin (2019) conducts a study on citizens' empowerment through people's participation in Union Parishad in Bangladesh. On the basis of the constitution, the author predominantly demonstrates the difference between the traditional concept of people's participation and modern practices of people's participation in field administration in Bangladesh. As well, the author explores the different avenues of people's participation in local government. The study was conducted by following a descriptive and analytical approach, whereas the findings reveal that community members' participation in local

government institutions is not only an opportunity for them, but also a mechanism for their empowerment. In addition, people's participation status in Union Parishad was very frustrating. However, the study was only focused on how empowerment of marginalized people occurred through people's participation in local government, but the author did not clarify the issues of people's participation in different avenues (Uddin, 2019).

Respectively, Hao et al. (2022) argue about the implication of people's participation in the governance process in terms of ensuring sustainable development in Kenya. The authors predominantly illustrate the world's current practices of people's participation in democratic process, decision-making process, policy formulation and implementation process. Then the authors highlight the practices of people's participation in Kenya with constitutional basis. The study was carried out by following a quantitative approach whereas the findings of the study demonstrate the impact and relationship between people's participation and sustainable development in Kenya. However, the study was conducted in Kenyan settings and ignored the concept of local government and good governance (Hao et al., 2022).

4.2 Major Challenges of People's Participation in the Union Parishads

Haque (2009) describes a study on the difficulties associated with citizen engagement in local governance. Initially, the author explains the concept of local governance, the actors of governance, and the role of local governance in socio-economic development. Principally, the author illustrates the poor status of the local government system in Bangladesh. The author contends that due to central government negligence, ineffective decentralization, weak economic independence, and limited government practice, local government institutions are frequently overshadowed by national policies, practices, and efforts at economic growth and social and political development. The study was conducted by analyzing secondary data, whereas the findings demonstrate that due to inefficiency, lack of resources, and political corruption, Union Parishads became ineffective and questioned by the general public. Furthermore, the findings reflect the status of various standing committees in terms of people's participation and decision-making in Union Parishad. However, although the author demonstrates a policy framework, he did not highlight the advances in people's participation in local government in terms of ensuring good governance in Bangladesh (Haque, 2009). In addition, Uzzaman (2010) discusses a study on the challenges of citizen participation in fostering good governance in developing nations. The author mainly examines stakeholders' perceptions on encouraging people to participate in local development projects along with a number of obstacles. The study was carried out by following a qualitative method. The study's findings revealed that the idea of good governance in Bangladesh is still relatively vague and confusing due to the conventional mindset of relevant stakeholders. As a result, the author places a strong emphasis on how individuals participate in development efforts in developing nations like Bangladesh. However, the author did not highlight the avenues of people's participation in terms of ensuring effective good governance in Bangladesh (Uzzaman, 2010).

Similarly, Panday and Rabbani (2011) explore a study on good governance at the grass-root level in Bangladesh, incorporating the instance of Union Parishad. In order to develop the body of knowledge on local government, the authors illustrate the four indicators of good governance—public engagement, leadership, transparency, and equality. The research was done using qualitative data, and its results indicate that the governance environment at the local level in Bangladesh is not conducive to the development of good governance and strong local democracy. In particular, the findings of the study demonstrate that although certain elements (such as ward Shaba, open budget, citizen charter, and freedom to information) were included in the Local Government (Union Parishad) Act of 2009, the government has not succeeded in ensuring participation, accountability, good governance, and openness. However, the authors did not provide any comprehensive suggestions to address the issues of people's participation in the Union Parishad regarding enhancing good governance in Bangladesh (Panday & Rabbani, 2011).

4.3 Initiatives for Ensuring Good Governance in Union Parishad through People's Participation

From a localism perspective, Lawton and Macaulay (2014) conducted a study on how people's participation enhances good governance in local government. The authors articulate that people's participation is a crucial factor in local integrity and governance. The study was conducted by following a case study in the United Kingdom, whereas the findings indicate that standards committees influenced the procedures and practices of local integrity governance via the active participation of local people. In fact, the authors say that standards committees are essential for getting people involved locally and making governance better. However, the authors did not clarify the dimension of different avenues of people's participation regarding enhancing good governance (Lawton & Macaulay, 2014). Besides, Poto and Fornabaio (2017) describe a study on the importance of people's participation as the key factor in enhancing good governance. In particular, the authors depict the context of the global good governance dimension in terms of increasing indigenous people's involvement in the environmental governance process. The study was carried out by following the case study method, whereas the findings reveal the implication of new technologies in people's participation as well as decision-making. In addition, the findings of the study recommend that easier access to information, greater engagement, and new forms of involvement, peaceful resolution, and environmental preservation may boost the participation of indigenous peoples in the process of strengthening good governance. However, the authors ignored the issue of people's participation in local government in terms of enhancing good governance (Poto & Fornabaio, 2017). Similarly, Hao et al. (2022) argue that civic education can enhance the consolidation of public consciousness in the governance process. Besides, the authors recommend that, since the Office of Public Engagement Rapporteur (OPP) plays a commendable role in collecting people's and leaders' perspectives, establishing the OPP can increase people's participation in the governance process (Hao et al., 2022).

4.4 Identification of the Research Gap

Throughout the literature review, it has been found that no particular study has been conducted yet to explore the state of avenues of people's participation in local government in terms of ensuring good governance. The author contemplates that although these studies predominantly focused on the general aspect of good governance and people's participation, there is a glaring lack of studies that can serve as a model for elucidating the factors that enhance the sustained level of good governance through people's participation in local government. Also, it has been found that most of the studies that have been done in the past have either looked at issues of good governance or looked at issues of people's participation. However, no study has yet been done to look at how people's participation in local government institutions in Bangladesh affects good governance. Therefore, this study focuses on the people's participation in rural local government to identify the current status of the avenues of people's participation regarding enhancing good governance in Bangladesh.

5. Research Questions

- a) How do people participate in local government (particularly Union Parishads) in Bangladesh to ensure good governance?
- b) How can we evaluate the public's sense of engagement in the various UPs avenues?
- c) In terms of implementing good governance in Bangladesh, what are the greatest obstacles to people's engagement in Union Parishads (UPs)?

6. Materials and Methods

The study has been conducted using a quantitative approach on the basis of the positivism philosophy, where an exploratory research approach has been applied. The quantitative approach has been applied to collect survey data. Quantitative studies provide data that is expressed in numbers, and the researcher is able to apply statistical tests in preparing statements about the data. Particularly, another reason for choosing the quantitative approach is that it is helpful in preparing descriptive statistics and inferential analysis (Demetrius Madrigal, 2020). In addition, by applying a quantitative approach, the researcher can get valid, and reliable results from the data analysis. Therefore, to attain the principal objective of this study, the quantitative method has been applied in an exploratory manner. However, survey data has been collected from the local people who belong to the selected Union Parishad in Bangladesh. A total of 120 respondents from two selected Union Parishads (Trishal and Osmanpur Unions) in Trishal Upazilla and Kuliarchar Upazila took part in the survey.

Figure 1: Study Area (Islam et al., 2017); (Portal, 2023)

Since the data were collected during the lockdown amid the pandemic, the researcher could not reach more respondents. Similarly, it is worth mentioning that the respondents were general people (government employees, day laborers, businessmen, and members of civil society) who belonged to the particular study areas and that the researcher selected them randomly. In this spirit, it is also mentioned that the research area was chosen on purpose. Due to the fact that no prior research on this issue has been undertaken in this region, this region was purposefully chosen for the study. Indeed, the researcher contemplates that it is enough to establish the proposition by only collecting information from the local people. However, close-ended questions were applied to collect survey data. Finally, data has been analyzed using MS Excel and SPSS software. Conversely, to ensure the balance between the probable threats of research and the possible benefits of research, all ethical issues have been maintained strictly.

7. Findings of the Study

7.1 Demographic Information of the Respondents

Demographic data is considered significant information in any study since it reveals the overall status and conditions of the participants. However, the demographic information of the respondents is illustrated by evaluating gender, age, and profession.

³ Red colour area indicates the Trishal Upazila

⁴ Yellow color area indicates the Kuliarchar Upazila

Figure 2: Demographic Information of the Respondent (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The demographic characteristics of this research were measured by gender, age, education, and the respondents' profession (table 1). Gender distribution showed that there were more male respondents (n = 102, 85%) than females (n = 18, 15%). The majority of the respondents were aged between 31 and 40 (n = 62, 51.7%). Besides, most of the respondents were less knowledgeable, i.e. illiterate (n = 56, 46.7%), whereas merely 21.7% (n = 26) were knowledgeable and 8.3% (n = 10) had a higher educational background. In addition, most of the respondents were involved in business professions (n = 28, 40%) and day laborers (n = 28, 23.3%).

7.2 Understanding of Participation Avenues

Figure 3: Understanding of Participation Avenues (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above bar chart (figure 2) shows how much people in Bangladesh know about the different avenues they can take part in local government to improve good governance. According to the survey data, it was discovered that 100% of the population was aware of their right to access information (n =120, 100%), while the majority of people were familiar

with local government (n= 102, 85%), Ward Shaba (n = 104, 87%), and village court (n = 118, 98%). Conversely, the majority of people were unfamiliar with the UP standing committee (n = 114, 95%), open budget meeting (n = 94, 78%), and Union Parishad act (n = 100, 83%). These statistics imply that half of the total rural population is unaware of their entitlement to take part in various avenues aimed at promoting good governance and strengthening local government in Bangladesh.

7.3 Participation of Respondents in the Different Avenues of Local Government

The following bar chart (figure 3) illustrates the participation of respondents in the different avenues of local government in Bangladesh. Based on the survey, it found that the majority of the respondents participated in the local government election (n = 110, 92%) and village court activities (n = 54, 45%). People's participation in the pre-open budget meeting (n = 118, 98%), final open budget meeting (n = 118, 98%), Ward Shaba (n = 114, 95%), and standing committee (n = 116, 97%), on the other hand, was frustrating.

Figure 4: Participation of Respondents in the Different Avenues of Local Government (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

However, these statistics imply that most of the rural people do not participate in the Ward Shaba meetings, UP standing activities, and open budget meetings, which create colossal challenges in terms of ensuring good governance in Bangladesh.

7.4 The Importance of Voter Turnout in the UP Election to Ensure Good Governance

Figure 5: The importance of voter turnout in the UP election to ensure good governance (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

In terms of assessing the importance of voter turnout in the UP election to ensure good governance, the above bar chart (figure 4) demonstrates the perception of rural people. According to the survey data, it was found that 100% of the respondents (n =120, 100%) argued that in terms of ensuring good governance in Bangladesh, there is no alternative way to ensure people's participation in the governance process except through local government elections.

7.5 Public Participation in Open Budget Meetings is Essential to Ensure Good Governance

Figure 6: Public participation in open budget meetings is essential to ensure good governance (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above pie chart reveals the necessity of people's participation in the open budget meeting to ensure good governance in Bangladesh. According to the survey, it was found that a majority of the respondents (n = 92, 77%) argued that people's participation in the open budget meeting is essential to ensure good governance in Bangladesh, whereas only a small group of people (n = 6, 5%) overruled this opinion.

7.6 The Importance of Citizen Engagement in Ward Shaba to Ensure Good Governance

The following line chart (figure 6) demonstrates the importance of citizen engagement in Ward Shaba with regard to ensuring good governance in Bangladesh. According to the survey data, it was found that a majority of the respondents (n = 90, 75%) believe that people's participation in Ward Shaba is an important mechanism to ensure good governance in Bangladesh. Conversely, a small group of people (n = 22, 18%) argued that only people's participation in the Ward Shaba wouldn't ensure good governance in Bangladesh.

Figure 7: The importance of citizen engagement in Ward Shaba to ensure good governance (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

7.7 Existing Status of the Village Court regarding Ensuring Good Governance

Figure 8: Existing status of the village court regarding ensuring good governance (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above pie chart shows the existing status of village court performances in terms of ensuring good governance in Bangladesh. Based on the survey results, it was found that a large group of respondents (n = 114, 95%) articulate that village court plays an imperative role in terms of carrying out good governance activities through people's participation in the local government institution in Bangladesh. Although a minor group (n = 6, 5%) debates

about this issue, it seems right that the village court plays a praiseworthy role in terms of enhancing good governance in rural areas in Bangladesh.

7.8 The Social Problems may be Resolved by the Village Court

In terms of addressing social issues, village courts play a noteworthy role in rural areas in Bangladesh. According to the given line chart (figure 8), it was found that the majority of the respondents (n = 112, 93%) believe that village court is an essential mechanism in local government institutions to fix the social issues that also play a substantial role in promoting good governance in Bangladesh. In contrast, a small minority (n = 6, 5%) criticizes the role of the village court in promoting good governance in Bangladesh.

Figure 9: The social problems may be resolved by the village court
(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

7.9 Participation of the Populace in Village Court is Essential for Ensuring Good Governance

Similarly, the following bar chart (figure 9) highlights the importance of people's participation in village court in terms of ensuring good governance in Bangladesh. According to the survey data, a large group of respondents (n =118, 98%) believe that people's participation in village court activities can certainly play an important role in terms of promoting good governance in Bangladesh. Since village court activities are open to all, the respondents trust on its performance regarding enhancing good governance in Bangladesh.

Figure 10: Participation of the populace in village court is essential for ensuring good governance (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

7.10 Participation of the public in the UP Standing Committee is Essential to Implement Good Governance

Figure 11: Participation of the public in the UP-Standing Committee is essential to implement good governance (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above pie chart (figure 10) depicts the significance of the people's participation in the UP-standing committee in terms of ensuring good governance in Bangladesh. Based on the survey results, a large group of homogeneous respondents ($n = 82$, 68%) articulate that participation of the rural community in the UP-Standing Committee is indispensable to promote good governance in Bangladesh. Remarkably, it was found that around 22% ($n = 26$) of the respondents did not say anything on these issues, although a small group of respondents ($n = 6$, 10%) thought that people's participation in the UP-standing committee is not effective in terms of enhancing good governance in Bangladesh.

7.11 Necessity of Accessing People's Participation in Information for Enhancing Good Governance

Figure 12: Necessity of accessing people's participation in information for enhancing good governance (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above bar chart (figure 11) demonstrates the importance of people's participation in A2I (access to information) in terms of enhancing good governance in Bangladesh. According to the survey results, 100% of the respondents (n = 120, 100%) believe that people's access to information ensures the transparency of government services, which may accelerate the practice of good governance at the grass root level in Bangladesh.

7.12 Respondent has Difficulties Getting Information

Figure 13: Respondent has difficulties getting information (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above bar chart (figure 12) shows whether citizens face challenges in terms of accessing a2i. According to the survey data, almost half of the respondents (n = 34, 28%)

face challenges in terms of accessing A2I for their required information. Although the majority of respondents stated that they have easy access to the A2I, the reality varies depending on the nature of the information. In this regard, the limitations behind access to A2I may limit the practice of good governance in Bangladesh.

7.13 The Gap between Policy Formulation and Implementation

Figure 14: The gap between policy formulation and implementation (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above pie chart (figure 13) illustrates the gap between policy formulation and implementation regarding people's participation and ensuring good governance in Bangladesh. This is the most important finding of the study. According to the survey data, a majority of the respondents (n = 80, 65%) contemplate that there is a comprehensive gap between policy formulation and implementation in terms of ensuring people's participation and good governance in local government in Bangladesh. This statistic clearly implies that regarding ensuring good governance in Bangladesh, the gap between policy formulation and implementation should be addressed in a proper way.

7.14 Awareness of the Right to Information Act (2009) Among the Public

Figure 15: Awareness of the right to information act (2009) among the public (Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above bar chart (figure 14) illustrates the public awareness of the right to information act (2009) in Bangladesh. Based on the survey results, it was found that 20% of the respondents (n =24, 20%) were unaware of the right to information act (2009). Although

the findings show that the majority of the respondents (n = 54, 45%) were aware of the right to information act (2009), they didn't know how to obtain information from the concerned authorities. Astonishingly, a large group of respondents (n = 42, 35%) did not provide their opinion on this issue.

7.15 Effective Strategy that can Ensure People's Participation as well as Good Governance

Figure 16: Effective strategy that can ensure people's participation as well as good governance
(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

This is another of the most significant findings of this study. The above bar chart (figure 15) reveals the significant strategy that can eliminate the issues of people's participation as well as ensure good governance in Bangladesh. Based on the survey results, it was found that the majority of respondents (n = 56, 46.7%) believe that people's education could be the best and most effective strategy to reduce the gap between policy formulation and implementation in Bangladesh. Similarly, a minor group of respondents argues that implementation of the law (n = 14, 11.7%) and people's awareness (n = 18, 15%) can be the best strategy in terms of ensuring people's participation and good governance in Bangladesh. In this vein, around 26.7% of the respondents (n = 32, 26.7%) articulate that people's awareness, law, and education together can be the best method to ensure people's participation and good governance in Bangladesh.

7.16 Discussion of the Study

The principal aim of this study was to explore the practice of people's participation in local government institutions (Union Parishad) in terms of ensuring good governance in Bangladesh. Since the Union Parishad is the lowest administrative entity in Bangladesh that provides services to the doorsteps of its inhabitants (Akhter & Ahmed, 2022), based on the survey results, it was found that most of the rural people have no idea about the different avenues of participation in local government units. In particular, the majority of the

population was unaware of their rights regarding participating in different avenues of local government. Even, most of the respondents did not participate in the Ward Shaba activities, UP standing committees' activities, open budget meetings, citizen charters, etc. Conversely, it was found that only an expected group of people participated in the village court activities and local government elections. In this context, the authors argue that without sustaining the participation of people in different avenues (i.e., Ward Shaba, UP standing committee, open budget meeting, village court, local government election, and citizen charter), local government institutions would fail to ensure good governance in Bangladesh. The study found that the main reasons behind the majority of people's unawareness are poor educational backgrounds (46.7%), a lack of concern for participation (95% in the UP standing committee, 78% in the open budget meeting, and 83% in the UP act), and a lack of self-interest that is conclusively illustrated in the demographic information and major findings sections, i.e., figures 1, 2, and 3. According to the findings, the study, therefore, suggests that the central government, as well as concerned authorities, should ensure the people's equitable participation in the different avenues in terms of ensuring good governance in Bangladesh.

8. Implications of the Study

In Bangladesh, Union Parishad is the lowest tier local government institution which delivers services to citizens at their entrance. It is also the largest service sector in the country, and this sector is continuously performing in terms of the number of challenges (Ferdous et al., 2022). In this setting, Union Parishad requires a great deal of attention, attachment, commitment, and determination to accomplish good governance at the grassroots level via effective engagement of the people. The cornerstone of establishing effective governance is people's participation, whereas Union Parishad plays a crucial role in this process as a rural local government unit. People may express their views, rights, and demands and secure their active participation in the government's decision-making process via participation (Asaduzzaman, 2008). This study provides a comprehensive idea about people's participation in local government units (Union Parishad) for ensuring good governance in Bangladesh. In particular, the findings of the study would help to develop the practical and theoretical insight of the learners. At the same time, these findings will help policymakers develop appropriate policies regarding enhancing people's participation in local government. In this spirit, the contribution of this research is very significant and pragmatic for ensuring good governance through people's participation in local government sectors (Union Parishad) in Bangladesh.

9. Conclusion and Recommendations

Good governance refers to a process of assuring government commitment and establishing a system that safeguards civil liberties and human rights, reduces corruption, considers the perspectives of all people, especially minorities, and increases transparency as well as government accountability. This study sought to explore how people's participation strengthens good governance in the field of administration in Bangladesh. In particular, the

findings of the study demonstrate the different avenues of people's participation in the field administrative units and the current status of people's participation regarding enhancing good governance at the grassroots level in Bangladesh. According to the survey data, it has been observed that most of the rural people were unaware of local government acts, UP standing committees, and open budget meetings, which limit the scope of their participation in different avenues of local government. Despite the fact that many rural residents were aware of the UP's operations, those of the UP-village court, rights to access information, and Ward Shaba activities, they were nevertheless denied access to the basic services provided by the field administrative units in Bangladesh. Since people's participation is the precondition of ensuring good governance, concerned authorities must strengthen the local people's participation in decision-making in the different avenues through incorporating effective mechanisms, i.e., ensuring public awareness, citizen charter, and the application of the rule of law. Based on analyzing the findings, the authors make a number of recommendations to increase public engagement in local government organizations and advance good governance in Bangladesh.

First and foremost, since most rural people are unaware of their participation rights, local government units should make the appropriate efforts to increase public awareness of their participation rights in different local government avenues. Secondly, based on the findings and discussion, the researchers argue that to encourage people's engagement in different avenues of local government, local government officials should restrict grouping, nepotism, and rural provocative political activities. Thirdly, concerned authorities should provide a conducive environment for rural people's participation in Ward Shaba, the UP-standing committee, the financial budget session, and the village court. Fourthly, in order to increase local government competency, central-local ties, and effective people's participation in Bangladesh, current patron-client relationships in local government institutions should be balanced. Fifthly, local government authorities' collaboration, synchronization, and professionalism should be strengthened to achieve good governance by assuring people's participation in field administrative units. Last but not least, Local government bodies should ensure the transparency of all their activities so that people's trustworthiness can enhance on local government's performance. In this regard, transparency of local government activities would boost good governance practices in Bangladesh.

Conflict of Interest

There aren't any instances of plagiarism, and the material is entirely unique. In addition, the authors state that they have no competing interests with regard to the study, their authorship, or the publishing of this manuscript.

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